

NEW TRENDS OF TEACHING ENGLISH: STUDENT-CENTERED AND TEACHER-CENTERED CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *This text explores the concept of classroom management as a multi-faceted process involving physical environment, routines, relationships, and behavior management. It presents a continuum of classroom management approaches, ranging from teacher-centered (custodial) to student-centered (humanistic). The teacher-centered approach emphasizes control, authority, and compliance, while the student-centered approach prioritizes active learning, mutual respect, and student autonomy. The text discusses the characteristics of each approach, including instructional methods, classroom design, rule-making, and disciplinary practices. It acknowledges that pure forms of either approach are rare, but these lenses offer valuable insights into the dominant orientation of a classroom.*

Keywords: *classroom management, teacher-centered, student-centered, custodial, humanistic, pupil control ideology, discipline, instructional methods, classroom design, rules and routines, punishments, compliance, autonomy, active learning, mutual respect.*

Classroom management is a multi-faceted concept that includes the organization of the physical environment, the establishment and routines, the development of effective relationships, and the prevention of and response to misbehavior.

Some researchers suggest that it is helpful to view classroom management beliefs and practices on a continuum from teacher-centered to student-centered. For example, Willower (1975) found that educators vary along a continuum of beliefs about the way children learn to behave and conceptualize this as one's pupil-control ideology. At one end of the continuum is the custodial (teacher-centered) educator and at the

other end is the humanistic (student-centered) educator. The extremes in the continuum of beliefs are described in the following way:

a) The educator with a custodial orientation is likely to be highly controlling. Employing punitive sanctions, moralistic perceptions, highly impersonal relationships with students, attitudes of general mistrust and a major focus on the maintenance of order.

b) The educator with a more humanistic orientation is likely to maintain a classroom climate in which active interaction and communication, close personal relationships with students, mutual respect, positive attitudes, and flexibility of rules, as well as student self-discipline, self-determination and independence are fostered (Willower, E, & Hoy, 1967). Custodialism and humanism are measured by the Pupil Control Ideology form, comprised of 20 statements, each followed by a like scale ranging from strongly agree (five points) to 'strongly disagree' (one point). A high score signifies a custodial attitude toward pupil control and a low score indicates a humanistic attitude toward control of pupils.

Similarly, Wolfgang (2001) identifies three philosophical "faces" of discipline, which include relationship-listening, confronting - contracting and rules -consequences. These three philosophical "faces" of discipline may be placed on a power continuum from minimum (student-centered) to maximum (teacher-centered) use of power by the teacher.

The relationship between a Teacher-Centered and Student - Centered approach in Classroom Management

Classroom management can be seen as opposite ends of a continuum, it is highly unlikely that any teacher implements a teacher-centered or student-centered approach to classroom management in its purest form . Nevertheless, these lenses are useful ways of examining the dominant orientation of a classroom.

In teacher-centered classrooms, control is of primary importance and "authority is transmitted hierarchically" (Dollard & Christensen, 1996, p. 3), meaning the teacher exerts control over the students.

Critics of teacher-centeredness argue that in these Classrooms, compliance is valued over initiative and passive learners over active

learners (Freiberg, 1999).

To help teachers maintain control over students, instructional methods that promote a focus on the teacher are frequently used, such as lectures, guided discussions, demonstrations and “cookbook” labs (Edwards, 2004). These forms of in structure lend themselves to having the teacher stand in the front of the classroom while all students work on the same task. Similarly, the physical design of the classroom often promotes a focus on the teacher and limits student activity that disrupts

that focus. In other words, rooms are often organized so that desks face toward the primary focal point, the teacher (Booster, 1991).

In addition, teachers exert their control through a system of clearly defined rules, routines and punishments that are mandated rather than developed with the students (Freiberg, 1999).

Generally, teachers identify the rules necessary for an orderly classroom and time is set aside for the teaching of these rules during the first several days of school. When students exhibit undesirable behavior, advocates of a teacher-centered approach often rely on punishments, such as reprimands, frowns, time outs and loss of special privileges (L. 1990).

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